

WALNUT

factsheet

SEWAGE SLUDGE

Smart BBF system

Introduction

As the population grows, agronomic activities are expected to drastically increase. The United Nations predicts that by 2050, the global population will reach 9.7 billion people and according to data from FAO, feeding this population will require a 70% increase in food production. To do so, fertiliser production will need to be stepped up and more sustainable alternatives found.

The Haber-Bosch process, used to synthesise ammonia for nitrogen (N) fertilisers, is highly energy-intensive, relying heavily on fossil fuels and contributes approximately 1.4% of global CO₂ emissions. Using alternative nitrogen sources as recovered-N from waste water treatment plants (WWTP) can slash the carbon footprint of agricultural production. What's more, phosphate rock, the main source of phosphorus (P) in conventional fertilisers, is a non-renewable resource, with some estimates suggesting that economically viable reserves may be depleted within the next 50 -100 years. Alternative sources of P such as recovered struvite from WWTP provide a slow-release source of phosphorus that helps conserve natural phosphate reserves and minimises water contamination. For all these reasons, the alternative proposed by Cetaqua as part of the WalNUT project is based on using N and P recovered from WWTP to produce a smart bio-based fertiliser (BBF) in combination with plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPBs), which are microorganisms that enhance nutrient availability, improve soil structure, and stimulate root growth.

Technology

The solids from the **raw wastewater (RW) are removed**, and the pre-treated feedstock flows through a **zeolite-filled column**. In the column, soluble N in the form of NH_4^+ is adsorbed onto the zeolite, along with other compatible cations like K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} . The nitrogen concentration in the effluent is continuously monitored, and when zeolite saturation is reached (indicated by increased NH_4^+ in the outflow), adsorption stops. **Desorption begins with a NaOH solution**, raising the pH to 11-12 and producing a **nitrogen-concentrated permeate**. This permeate is fed into the PP hollow fibre membrane contactors (HFMC) for **ammonium sulfate production**. Sulphuric acid flows inside the fibres in a countercurrent direction to the permeate, allowing ammonia to diffuse through the membrane pores and react with sulfuric acid to form ammonium sulphates $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Although this ammonium-rich solution is a marketable product, the technology aims to optimise nitrogen recovery using zeolites and HFMC while developing a value-added fertiliser. By **mixing recovered struvite, ammonium sulphate, and four plant growth-promoting bacteria strains, a Smart BBF system is created**, potentially controlling the rate, timing and duration of nutrient release.

Characteristics

Recovering NH_4^+ from the anaerobic digester effluents of a WWTP to produce ammonium sulphate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ as a fertiliser offers multiple environmental, economic, and operational advantages. Additionally, incorporating this ammonium sulphate into a Smart BBF with PGPBs and struvite $(\text{MgNH}_4\text{PO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O})$ provides further benefits.

Producing ammonium sulphate from rejected water from the anaerobic digester's digestate could potentially **reduce ammonium discharges** into water bodies, reduce energy consumption linked to aerobic N-removal systems and offer a **more sustainable alternative to conventional fertilisers** produced by the Haber-Bosh method.

In addition, blending this ammonium sulphate with recovered struvite (as a source of P) and PGPB could promote **controlled nutrient release, improve plant nutrient uptake** and **soil fertility**, reduce freshwater eutrophication and increase crop yield.

Field test

These field trials are being conducted on cereal, legume, and brassica crops, grown in microplots across three distinct environments. This will enable a comprehensive comparison of the effects of the recovered fertilisers against conventional fertilisers and amendments, providing valuable insights into their agronomic performance and potential benefits. The upcoming results are promising and will contribute to a better understanding of the role of these recovered nutrients in sustainable agricultural practices.

WALNUT

factsheet

SEWAGE SLUDGE

june 2025

Credits

Alicia González Mñiguez · Project manager at CETAQUA

walnutproject.eu

info@walnutproject.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000752.